

A REVIEW OF BATTERY FIRES IN ELECTRIC VEHICLES FAULT DETECTION AND SAFETY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract:

In recent days, more cases have occurred in the burst of electric vehicles. The burst is due to the battery expanding a little while charging. The battery is made of lithium-ion batteries and three main parts are in the battery, they are anode, cathode and separator. When the battery is discharged, the separator creates the pressure that makes anode and cathode connect to each other, it leads to short circuit, so the battery bursted. So an accident occurs. To prevent this accident we want to know further, when the vehicle will burst. To set the alert device in the battery, that device made up of a thermistor and alert device contains the sensor. Sensors are used to control , monitoring and safety. That alert device is connected with our mobile phones or any electronic devices. The alert device has a sound type called conventional strobe sounder. In this conventional strobe sounder has beacons provided audible. We can set the time in the alert device to one minute of battery's high pressure. That time is set by our wish only. And most important which device or mobile phones are connected by alert device that connected device notification sounds always will be in high. Because we are driving, we shouldn't hear the notification. So the volume of devices should be high. When the battery leads to high pressure, that pressure will transfer to the alert device. The alert device makes a sound and that alert message is sent to connected electronic devices or mobile phones. We can observe that sound or that message to escape from the accident. This alert device did not disturbed the battery. So it is only safe and makes our journey safe in electric vehicles.

Keywords: Electric battery, separator, sensors, alert device, thermistor, conventional strobe sounder, electronic devices, mobile phones, Gadgets